

Washability of Wearable Electronic Textiles

E. Ismar^{1,2}, S. K. Bahadir², F. Kalaoglu²

¹ Department of NanoScience & NanoEngineering, ITU, Maslak, Istanbul, Turkey

² Department of Textile Engineering, ITU, Gumussuyu, Istanbul, Turkey

Corresponding author: ismar@itu.edu.tr

Abstract The field of electronic textiles (e-textiles) gained huge impact during the last decades. For the concept of wearability, garments including e-textiles should be comfortable and have enough durability to wearer, and display resistance to regular textile maintenance processes. All these parameters should be also followed for the wearable e-textiles products to make them reliable. E-textiles are not only serving the humanity but also give facilitation to daily life basics. E-textiles have a huge variety of application areas from aviation to health monitoring systems. Besides all positive effects, they also have some drawbacks in terms of durability through the environmental conditions and user effects. Before introducing the e-textiles into the market, main problems such as fastness to washing, continuity and the reliability on the interconnections, and deformation issues should be well addressed. Thus, recently researchers concentrated on maintaining the performance of e-textiles over washing cycles. In this review, several examples of washable e-textiles are presented and also their drawbacks and advantages are discussed.

Keywords— Conductive yarns, e-textiles, smart textiles, reliability, washability of e-textiles.

I. INTRODUCTION

Smart textiles is an interesting topic due to their interdisciplinary role in different fields. Electronic textiles (e-textiles) is one of the most popular sub group of smart textiles and it basically combines the electronics with textile products [1]. Figure 1 schematically explains the integration of wearable textiles.

Fig. 1: The wearable system from a technological point of view [2].

Rigid electronic components combined with the flexible textiles are considered the novelty for building a flexible electronics. With the developing technologies, clothes became not only a basic item; they shaped into smart materials thanks to the combination of electronics. Electronic textiles can serve as a local monitoring and basic computation system, they can find a place in wireless communication and sensor applications and while they are embedded in the form of wearable textiles [3], [4].

As it can be seen from the chart in Figure 1, wearable systems can be attached to the accessories or integrated into the clothing. Examples of attached accessories are belts, some parts of the vest, and so on. while not requiring any resistance to washing due to their re-attachable form. The other part of electronic systems can be integrated into the garments which may be washed during their lifecycles thus, their washability should be investigated.

E-textiles should be developed according to the fact that they can be able to withstand the stresses of use and they should be able to be worn and washed [5]. Moreover, e-textile component varies from different material types. Thus, material to be washed, can be conductive yarn, printed circuit board, fabric with conductive coating, embroidery or so on [6], [7]. In Figure 2, detail explanations are presented as a diagram. Conductivity feature can be gained before or after fabrication of the fabric. If conductivity feature is added after

production, then it can be applied via coating with conductive polymeric structures or sewing/embroidered with conductive threads on the non-conductive fabric. Another option is fabrication the conductive fabric with embedded conductive materials such as conductive threads. These threads can be metallic or polymeric and polymeric ones are coated with inherently conductive polymers or metals. Variety of production routes are available for e-textiles. In that reason, it is not possible and easy to build a washing cycle which is suitable for all type of e-textile materials. They all require a unique gentle treatment according to their nature. Generally, low temperature washing cycles are recommended for the e-textiles.

Fig. 2: Techniques to embedded conductivity feature on the textiles [2].

There are lots of e-textile prototypes They are mostly in the research and development stage. For their commercialization, some challenges should be overcome. Before introducing the e-textiles to the market, main problems such as fastness to washing, interconnection problems, deformation issues should be well addressed. In that perspective, e-textiles must sustain the function of clothing while they have enough durability, resistance to regular textile maintenance process such as washing, and comfortability feature [8].

For example, smart jacket for neonatal which designed for the monitoring the ECG signals from the baby was designed with removable parts to prevent the damage of electronic parts during the washing process [9]. Also, they studied the differences between large silver electrode vs. small gold printed electrode for ECG measurements. They both give good ECG results with lower noise ratio however, washing performance is better for silver and it is also hypoallergenic where gold is not. After some washing cycles, the conductivity of the gold printed electrodes reduced due to corrosion of under layer metal [9].

As a first generation, integration of electronic components with textiles was maintained with robust and wash-proof re-attachable packing designs. Later on, all electronic components were transferred to the textile based designs [8]. The main point while building a commercially viable e-textiles is withstand them through the washing process together with the commercially available detergent and water [10].

Washing has an important role in the maintenance of the

textile products. In the aim of giving stability during the washing process, covering of conductive top layer of the e-textiles was studied. In a study, LED brightness and sensor signals were preserved for first washing cycle however silicon capsulation started to damage at 60 °C thus, the low range of temperatures, such as; 30 °C are recommended for washing of the e-textile products [10].

It is possible to get perfect results from conventional Ag/AgCl electrodes but their usage needs to be connected to several cables and between the skin and electrode, gel application is necessary. Substitute to that system, reliable textile electrodes are investigated and they present remarkable developments. Wearable electronic textiles are favorable due to their monitoring ability of ECG signals. This monitoring apparatus can be stitched through the underwear as a shirt or adapted on the belt which can be connected to the body close to the heart.

For obtaining flexible textile electrodes different fabric types and PEDOT:PSS coatings were studied previously. Preliminary studies showed that cotton fabrics are more adequate than the other due to their high absorbency of PEDOT:PSS solution [11]. After immersing the knitted fabric into the PEDOT:PSS solution conductivity feature is gained by the conventional textile fabric. PEDOT:PSS used as a conductive polymeric solution to bring the textiles conductivity feature. Different fabric compositions; cotton, polyester and polyamide were dip coated through the PEDOT:PSS solution and were used as an e-textile electrode. PEDOT:PSS treatment makes the fabrics suitable for ECG measurements due to its inherent conductivity property [11].

Fig. 3: Woven structure of fabric as a patch form which is consisted of non-conductive fibers and embedded copper fibers for measuring the body motions [12], [13].

For successful commercialization of e-textiles, washability of them has a key role [13]. Researchers also developed the prototype that allows the data transmission over the copper fibers as shown in Figure 3. Copper fibers have a role as a conductive fiber moreover they wrapped in a polymer coating which makes them more durable to the daily wearing and tearing forces. For this study, the joining of fibers is made with conventional soldering or adhesive techniques. The main problem of joining elements is to

create weak points against forces and washing process [13]. Authors highlighted that copper fibers which are embedded to fabric and covered with the polymeric coating are quite durable against the washing and are not damaged however the joining parts between fibers and electronic system elements were broken and they needed to be improved in terms of resistance to mechanical forces [13].

Furthermore, coated fabrics are highly related to the topology of knitting and/or weaving structure. Repeated folding and washing are resultant to decrease on the performance of the sensors and to improve the durability of them instead of coating the fabric, conductive fibers can be knitted on the base of non-conductive fibers. The cooperation of the conductive and non-conductive fibers may increase the sensing performance of the e-textile product together with the improvement on the washing performance of it [14].

Smart textiles have promising results in terms of utilization however, they have some complications while fabricating, and performance reduction after washing and folding. And aesthetic design difficulties are another challenge on smart textiles which makes their commercialization difficult [14].

Fig.4: Example of wearable knitted wireless system [16].

Also, flexible textile antennas were recently developed inside the textile based product to communicate via wireless systems which were resistant to 5 times washing cycle [15]. Figure 4 represents the schematic view of wearable knitted wireless electronics which is embedded to knitted fabric.

First generation products are generally re-attachable thus before the washing process it is possible to remove them from the textile. Thus, they are not affected by the washing process. However, re-attachable systems are not very favorable. On the other hand, for washing a bare electronic system components covering them with a thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) is a well-known and suggested technique to prevent them from chemical and mechanical

actions during the washing process [15].

II. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, for manufacturing reliable and wearable e-textile products, they should be able to withstand the stresses occurring during the manufacturing, wearing, and usage. Also they should be durable for the washing effects.

If one garment is reusable in terms of clothing, it means that during its lifecycle, it will be needed to be washed at least several times. Main challenge about wearable electronic textiles is that they are not stable enough for washing procedure. Indeed, high temperature and intensive washing cycles should not be followed for e-textiles products. Similar to fabrics requiring gentle washing treatments, e-textiles also require gentle washing treatments instead of intensive washing cycles since the damage may occur during washing particularly for silver plated conductive e-textile structures. Thus, gentle washing cycles with less forces and lower temperatures should be followed. Washing has an important role in the maintaining of the performance of the smart textile products. The fabricated system should be washable for the reusability of the product. For that reason, washing process should be examined in terms of applied forces during the washing process, the effect of used chemicals (detergent, softener etc.), washing time, water hardness, and temperature should be all together evaluated. Mathematical programming based on the data acquired from the experimental results can be helpful to define the effects of washing mechanism on the electronic wearable textiles.

If the e-textile products are not being washable it means that after the usage it should be replaced with the new one. And this is not a cost efficient way. Moreover, it is not environment friendly and economic solution. For preventing the squander of the e-textile products, they should be manufactured durable enough against washing process.

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